

1 **Xist is activated during resistance in triple negative breast cancer *in vitro*.**

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6 We recently described Xist induction (and in some cases its silencing), as a recurrent transcriptional event
7 associated with p53-deficient backgrounds, and demonstrated Xist activation is directly controlled by loss
8 of tumor suppressor (p53 or Rb) function. Xist expression is high soon after the onset of transformation; in
9 some cancer types, like breast cancer, its expression remains high while in others its expression levels
10 subside but remain detectable at clinical presentation of solid tumors. Xist activation is functionally
11 relevant, as it influences clonal selection early in disease evidenced by its control of subtype selection in
12 human breast cancer and human lung cancer. We used proteomic and transcriptomic techniques to
13 identify the existence of a putative Xist RNP complex in cancer whose composition varies based on
14 context and expression but whose major function appears to be modulation of interleukin enhancer factors
15 ILF2/3 and likely possesses epigenetic silencing and activation functions reminiscent of its function in
16 development but with a wider range of transcriptional targets.

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118 Resistance to treatment and disease relapse is a major problem in humans with cancer (solid tumor
119 disease). We demonstrate here that Xist activation is a transcriptional feature of disease resistance,
120 providing evidence that its activation is a quantitatively significant event in triple negative breast cancer
121 cells displaying resistance to treatment. Thus, in human cancer, Xist is activated and a function is
122 associated with this activation, at least twice: immediately after transformation, shaping clonal selection of
123 the founder clone during stages that shape subtype selection, then reactivating later in disease, after
124 treatment has begun, where its expression is enriched at high levels in TNBC patients with
125 treatment-resistant disease, indicating its function both in development of the tumor but as a
126 disease-modifying agent late in disease.

Results

Figure 1: Engineered drug resistance in vitro in TNBC cells results in Xist induction.

GSE206324

n=1 TNBC breast cancer cells (UACC3199)
n=2 TNBC breast cancer cells (n=1 paclitaxel and n=1 doxorubicin resistant)
(paclitaxelR: SUM159; doxR: SUM149)

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
7503	2.85E-06	1.595	-4.6811706	-7.4644957	960.1	XIST	82/25888	99.7

Figure 2a: Hormone deprivation in the serum coupled with endocrine therapy results in Xist silencing *in vitro*.

Cells were grown in charcoal stripped (hormone-deprived) media before drug treatment and subsequent RNA-sequencing.

GSE241942

n=3 CAMA-1 (luminal type)
n=3 CAMA-1 4OH-tamoxifen (active metabolite of tamoxifen)

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
7503	2.67E-18	0.295	8.724453	2.5733749	62.55	XIST	309/14925	97.9

Figure 2b: Hormone deprivation in the serum coupled with endocrine therapy with the next-generation ET agent elacestrant similarly results in Xist silencing.

GSE241942

n=3 CAMA-1
n=3 CAMA-1 elacestrant

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
7503	9.18e-15	0.3008	7.750173	2.33157694	61.84	XIST	78/14904	99.5

The data here are seemingly at odds with our demonstration that Xist expression is repressed by estrogen and activated following endocrine therapy *in vivo*, but consistent with our hypothesis that Xist expression is significantly modulated during endocrine therapy and by differences in tumor suppressor function and consistent with our initial finding which showed that changes in Xist expression are among the greatest quantitative differences in gene expression when comparing p53-sufficient and p53-deficient breast cancer cells, with Xist decreasing rather than increased in breast cancer cell lines with p53-deficient genetic background. The difference in the direction of Xist change following *in vitro* endocrine therapy exposure in breast cancer cells demonstrated here likely reflects a composite function of epigenetic machinery expressed at that time in the cell and differences in culture conditions (e.g., passage number) that results in a large magnitude change in Xist expression but with alternating induction or silencing.

Consistent with these findings, we found Xist modulation in a third *in vitro* model of hormone deprivation resulting from exposure to endocrine therapy agents. Here, like observed with tumor suppressor deletion or mutation, Xist expression was activated following engineered tamoxifen resistance in 3D spheroid culture opposed to short term ET exposure in traditional 2D culture.

Figure 3: Engineered tamoxifen resistance in 3D culture in hormone positive breast cancer cells results in significant Xist induction.

GSE165571

n=3 MCF7 (3D spheroid culture)
n=3 MCF7-TR (tamoxifen resistance; 3D spheroid culture)

GeneID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
7503	1.81E-13	0.491	-7.362344	-3.617189	33.54	XIST	2220/16775	86.8

Thus, exposure of triple negative breast cancer cells *in vitro* to widely used chemotherapies doxorubicin and paclitaxel results in Xist induction in response to exposure to either drug. Hormone deprivation via endocrine therapy (by at least two separate ET agents) results in silencing of Xist, with changes in culture conditions resulting in Xist induction in hormone positive breast cancer cells. Xist is activated during drug (chemotherapy) resistance in TNBC *in vitro*, and data from *in vitro* models indicates that Xist modulation during the course of treatment as a form of resistance is likely a conserved cellular behavior in hormone positive breast cancers.

Discussion

We demonstrated here that Xist is activated during engineered resistance to chemotherapy agents utilized for the treatment of triple negative breast cancer upon exposure of TNBC cells to the drug *in vitro*. The induction of Xist in these resistant environments was among the largest changes in the TNBC cell transcriptome. In an accompanying manuscript, we demonstrate that engineered resistance to trastuzumab results in and/or is accompanied by induction of the Xist non-coding RNA transcript, and that when comparing the tumor transcriptome of a small cohort of HER2+ patients based on clinical outcome (residual disease [RD] versus pathologic complete response [pCR]), Xist induction was similarly a feature of residual disease activity (treatment failure) in humans with HER2+ breast cancer *in vivo*.

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Methods

We utilized whole transcriptome methodologies with R-based computational quantitative methods in conjunction with RNA-sequencing and/or microarray-based technology (public or published) to measure total transcription in breast cancer cells for this study of Xist transcriptional dynamics in hormone receptor negative (triple negative) or hormone receptor positive breast cancer.